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Pilot repository for fragment screening data

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D82 (D26.10): Pilot repository for fragment screening data

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2 Introduction

Structural biologists have become much more productive and much more ambitious in terms of the size of the biological systems they study. This has resulted in generation of inter-related datasets with multiple structures (Jaskolski, *et al.*, 2022; Weiss, *et al.*, 2022). Datasets of multiple experimentally determined structures have been generated for many research projects. However, some structural biology approaches require many experiments leading to multiple macromolecular structures to derive scientific insight. Among these approaches are:

- Fragment-screening using X-ray crystallography or NMR spectroscopy.
- Time-resolved X-ray crystallography and its two subtypes:
 - Serial Synchrotron X-ray crystallography (SSX) datasets collected using microcrystals and microfocus beams at synchrotrons.
 - Serial Femtosecond X-ray crystallography (SFX) datasets collected using microcrystals and lasers at X-ray Free-Electron Laser (XFEL) facilities.

The structural biology community has a long history of archiving and making its data open access via the worldwide Protein Data Bank (wwPDB) managed core archive, the Protein Data Bank (PDB). Established in 1971, PDB is the single global archive of experimentally derived macromolecular structure models. The wwPDB is an international collaboration that manages the deposition, processing and distribution of three structural biology core archives, PDB, BMRB and EMDB. The founding members of the wwPDB are RCSB PDB (USA), PDBe (Europe) and PDBj (Japan). The Biological Magnetic Resonance Data Bank (BioMagResBank or BMRB) group (USA), specialized in NMR data archiving, joined the wwPDB in 2006. The Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) is a public repository for electron microscopy density maps of macromolecular complexes (3DEM; 3D reconstructions in Cryo-electron microscopy) and subcellular structures. EMDB was founded at EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) in 2002 and joined the wwPDB in 2021.

A key component that enables wwPDB to maintain archiving standards is the Protein Data Bank Exchange (PDBx)/macromolecular Cystallographic Information Framework (mmCIF), abbreviated to PDBx/mmCIF (Westbrook, *et al.*, 2022). This framework was developed to describe macromolecule structure associated with an individual experiment. Such individual experiment results in a single biomolecular structure model for X-ray diffraction experiments, a single model fitted to an electric potential map determined by Cryo-electron microscopy, or an ensemble of models all corresponding to a single set of restraints and chemical shifts determined with Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) methods. Each structure model or ensemble corresponds to specific experimental and sample setup that was performed at a certain point in time and received a unique identifier in the PDB archive.

All deposited data goes through a processing pipeline with standardization, annotation and validation processes, and these processes are all underpinned by the same PDBx/mmCIF file

format. This format is therefore amenable to modern data science approaches as it is computer-readable with well-defined data semantics described in a dictionary facilitating translation to various types of SQL databases and outputs in json, xml, csv formats for further analysis. The PDBx/mmCIF file format is nowadays fundamental for the delivery of a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) PDB to millions of users globally.

Embracing the “FAIR” principles encourages data resource developers and managers to carefully consider the data structures of their databases, so they support data interoperability and reuse, and additionally automated and comprehensive assessments of datasets. The [GO-FAIR initiative](#) provides a full description of the fundamental FAIR principles.

Structural biology-supported fragment screening is nowadays an important tool in pharmaceutical research, especially for discovering lead compounds and drug development. Historically only few tightly bound fragment-target complexes of very big fragment-screening campaigns ended up in the PDB, leaving much of the experimental findings largely unfindable, inaccessible and unused. Now, in the frame of their activities in iNEXT-Discovery, the data handling specialists from partner EMBL-EBI, also hosting the PDBe, set out to design a novel type of data repository, tailored to contain data for entire fragment screening campaigns.

This Deliverable reports on data infrastructure developments for such FAIR repository to handle fragment-screening multi-datasets. Eventually, the resulting pilot repository is foreseen to be a useful starting point to expand the wwPDB archiving standards further, to capture appropriate data for other “multi-dataset investigations” that would greatly benefit from description of additional metadata regarding the relationship that logically links the multiple datasets together. A key aspect for developing the pilot repository is therefore the leveraging of the mmCIF data framework for data standardization.

3 Fragment screening experimental data

Brief overview

Valuable insights from structural biology often means that low occupancy or heterogenous binding of chemicals (*e.g.* low molecular weight compounds, reaction intermediates, etc.) to macromolecules can be interpreted (Pearce, *et al.*, 2017; De Zitter *et al.*, 2022). Among the successful experimental approaches associated with this technological development is Fragment-Based Screening (FBS). FBS involves low molecular weight compounds, with low complexity (*e.g.* one or two functional groups) being screened against a biological target. By forming a complex with the biological target they could interfere with biological function. The ‘fragments’ or small chemicals in FBS, enable coverage of large chemical space with relatively few compounds, is relatively cheap and requires lower amounts of purified biological samples, which is helpful in case the supply of purified biological samples may be a limiting factor.

Fragment-based lead discovery (FBLD) combines biochemical FBS binding assays with atomic-level structural characterisation and other biophysical methodologies (ITC, DLS, DSC, MST, SPR, MS, ...) to discover “hits” that have the potential to be converted to “leads”. FBS is therefore a complex and data-rich endeavour, wherein each stage of the process can generate different types of complex data, in both raw and processed forms. The popularity of fragment screening being used against biological targets is reflected by the increasing number of facilities that support fragment screening experiments,; within iNEXT-Discovery:

- European Molecular Biology Laboratory (**EMBL**) Grenoble based at European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (service centre for X-ray crystallography, FR)
- XChem based at **Diamond** Light Source (service centre for X-ray crystallography, UK)
- Macromolecular Crystallography (BESSY-MX) at Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin/**HZB** (service centre for X-ray crystallography, DE)
- FragMAX and MicroMax based at MAX IV (service centre for X-ray crystallography, SE)
- Center for Biomolecular Magnetic Resonance (BMRZ, **GUF**, DE)

An aspect for developing our new data framework involved consultation and discussion with key stakeholders at the facilities above. With offering different methods and located at different sites, there is diversity with in-house data management strategies (*e.g.* SQL database, json files, etc.) used at these facilities. In consultation with the facilities, we have been exploring how to support capture and archiving of the rich datasets generated at their facilities for dissemination leveraging the PDBx/mmCIF data framework.

Data availability

Despite the plethora of data being generated, the majority of FBS data remains inaccessible to the external scientific community. Of note, high-throughput facilities, such as beamlines at synchrotrons have daily 100s of datasets being collected. These facilities provide internal data storage systems for their users, however, even if these datasets were publicly accessible, the datasets are formatted in schemes that are unique to each facility. Moreover, the FBS/FBLD approach is vulnerable to intractability with regards to chemical synthesis route or chemical purity, and these can result in no lead compounds being discovered. When this occurs, despite the rich dataset of protein and small molecule interactions being generated for each fragment screen, the data will likely end-up unpublished and publicly unavailable.

Whenever a fragment screen is being published, typically a subset of structures, such as one or few fragments hit that was/were developed into a lead compound, are deposited to the PDB, whereas the rest of the datasets remains either inaccessible or is made publicly available through non-standardised web portals. Even though they are often neglected as being 'negative results', these publicly in- or less-accessible datasets can be relevant for structure determination method development and can serve for instance as training datasets for AI methods development. Also, full FBLD projects can be efficiently used to assess whether a biological target or the class of biological target has druggable pockets or clefts, even when the target is considered challenging, like for shallow invaginations that can occur at protein-protein interfaces (Wang *et. al*, 2023). If FBS datasets are not published, the experimental analysis of a potential interesting biological target will end-up being inaccessible to the wider scientific community. In any case, even the availability of data from costly studies that reveal no screening hits may still be useful to other, for instance by preventing redundant research activities.

4 Databases and data standards

Following data dictionaries and data standards

Fundamental to standardising data in the wwPDB database has been the development of a *data dictionary* containing a complete set of semantic definitions and descriptions (Bourne *et al.*, 1997). Such *data dictionary* enables the validation of each item by (manual or) programmatic checking of data integrity by parsing and checking data files. For example, data

values can be validated for data type and, where appropriate, checked against a set of controlled vocabulary. Additionally, semantic relationships between different data items can be validated.

Data dictionaries and limitations of PDB file format: a legacy structural biology format

The PDB data format introduced in the 1970's has a rigid definition of data tables in fixed column-positions. Also, the number of characters in each line of the file is restricted (originally due to the size of the physical punched cards used to store information in the 1970s). This not only meant that the data format was not amenable to modern data management approaches, but the semantic relationships were not defined between different records in a manner that is amenable to computation approaches for validating data content.

As a computationally parsable definition of the PDB format was not available, software developers had to hard-code in their applications their own interpretation of the file format. Since then, amongst the challenging aspects of the legacy file format is the diversity of metadata that is embedded in lines in the file, which all began with 'REMARK'. The PDB format itself was therefore frozen in 2011 at version 3.3, and no future updates are being planned.

wwPDB and mmCIF data dictionaries

In the 1990's the original PDB file format's limitations started to become apparent and the work on a new data standard was started. The International Union of Crystallography (IUCr) established a committee dedicated to create a new data model for macromolecular data generated using X-ray crystallography. This resulted in the macromolecular Crystallographic Information File (mmCIF), with an accompanying mmCIF data dictionary containing over 3000 data items (Bourne *et al.*, 1997). Over time, terms for NMR and cryo-EM were added, and the dictionary was renamed PDBx/mmCIF. PDBx/mmCIF has continued to be adopted, and in 2011 the major X-ray structure determination software developers agreed to have PDBx/mmCIF as standard output from their programs. The PDBx/mmCIF data dictionary has recently been further expanded to support also the archiving of computed structure models (Vallat *et al.* 2023), and other data archives, like the Small Angle Scattering Biological DataBank (SASBDB; Kachala *et al.*, 2016), have incorporated a PDBx/mmCIF framework. Conveniently, the PDBx/mmCIF data format also underpins the information for any modeled small-molecule ligand found in/bound to a macromolecule structure in the wwPDB database. The PDBx/mmCIF defined chemical definitions are kept in a reference dictionary, the [Chemical Component Dictionary \(CCD\)](#).

mmCIF data structure

The PDBx/mmCIF format is fundamentally based on the STAR procedure (Self-defining Text Archive and Retrieval; Hall *et al.*, 1997), a standard ASCII-based text format which uses key-value pairs to define data names and data values. An important feature is that data names for values are composed of two parts, namely 'data category name' and 'data item name'. In the PDBx/mmCIF data framework, a data item is a unit of data description, and each data item name has a corresponding value or values. Related data items are listed together in a data category that can be usefully visualised as a tabular data structure with multiple rows where each data item is a heading for a column, or a list of name-value pairs with each value being described by the data item.

The flexibility of the PDBx/mmCIF data format to either capture data as either list or as multi-rowed tables is likely among the reasons it has been used in various structural biology contexts. In addition, a key strength of the mmCIF framework is that it can be extended with

relative ease while maintaining the same software accessible to the data dictionary, and thus supporting both database infrastructure and downstream and upstream applications. The new data standards that we have developed to underpin our fragment-screening pilot repository are an extension of the core PDBx/mmCIF dictionary.

5 Fragment screening data archiving infrastructure

Extending the PDBx/mmCIF dictionary for fragment screening campaigns

An overview of the newly designed data structure is illustrated in Figure 1, and part of our proposed extension to the original PDBx/mmCIF dictionary is in Table 1. The top layer of the new data structure in Table 1 will be applicable to any “multi-structure investigation”, so not just to fragment screening experiments. The dictionary extension described in Table 1 enables linkages to other databases where more details that pertain to a single experiment are captured. Critical contextual information is captured in the form of the description of sample components: macromolecular composition (polymers, *i.e.* protein, RNA, DNA) and chemical components (non-polymer components). Defining new data categories (*i.e.* tables / lists of related items), and the data items (name-value pairs) is key to extending the PDBx/mmCIF dictionary to meet the needs of representing additional metadata. Each data category reflects either a table of data or useful grouped sets of name-value pairs.

As mentioned, the new data categories should be relevant to any multi-structure investigation, and fragment screening experiments represent just one type of these. Therefore, we have prepared a distinct set of data categories (‘_pdbx_fraghub_investigation’ listed in Table 2) that are specific for fragment screening experiments. The intention is that these new fragment screening data items and data categories will form another extension to the PDBx/mmCIF dictionary, distinct but related to the one that is specific to all investigations. This level of separation will allow the fragment screening dictionary to evolve independently with unique sets of mandatory items and controlled vocabularies from the outset.

Table 1. Categories common to all “investigations”

Data category	Brief description
_pdbx_investigation	Simple top-level data, primarily containing a persistent accession code and a title.
_pdbx_investigation_focus	Information/focus concerning the whole screening project (<i>i.e.</i> shared target(s). Includes information like name(s) for common target(s); can include cross-reference to the identifier(s) for the target in another database (<i>e.g.</i> Uniprot).
_pdbx_investigation_archived_data	IDs for in-file use to define links to data in other databases.
_pdbx_investigation_sample	Describes the precise combination of polymers and small molecules that is common for a subset of the data, by referring to subcategories. This description will exclude the differing component between the structures in a way that is specific to the

investigation subtype. For example, in a fragment screening investigation the description here excludes the chemical definition for the fragment(s) as this can differ between experiments.

<code>_pdbx_investigation_poly_descript</code>	In-file IDs to define the combination of macromolecules/polymers present in one or more datasets.
<code>_pdbx_investigation_entity_poly</code>	Category that lists polymeric components (protein, DNA, RNA, ...) in the datasets. Gives each combination an ID for in-file use. Contains information like macromolecule type, descriptors (e.g. FASTA-type sequence) and cross-reference identifier(s) for other databases, if available.
<code>_pdbx_investigation_nonpoly_descript</code>	IDs for in-file use to define the combination of ligands/non-polymers present in one or more datasets.
<code>_pdbx_investigation_entity_nonpoly</code>	Category that lists non-polymeric components found in datasets and gives them an ID in-file use. Contains information like names, descriptors (InChIKey), formulae, molecular weights, ...

Figure 1. Overview of the data dictionary describing a “fragment screening investigation”

Table 2. Categories specific to fragment screening datasets

Data category	Brief description
<code>_pdbx_fraghub_investigation_campaign</code>	Captures different screening campaigns being performed at different facilities, potentially involving multiple chemical

	libraries. Contains information like the facility and year when the campaign began.
<code>_pdbx_fraghub_investigation_series</code>	Groups experiments that are part of screening particular target against a particular chemical library. Contains information like fragment chemical library identifiers and batch numbers.
<code>_pdbx_fraghub_investigation_screening_exp</code>	Aggregated items specific to one structural biology dataset. Describes the precise combination of fragment sets, polymers and other small molecules for an experimental instance. Includes IDs to link to external data in relevant databases, such as a PDB entry with an experimentally determined structure.
<code>_pdbx_fraghub_investigation_screening_result</code>	Result captured per experiment in terms of hit assessment.
<code>_pdbx_fraghub_investigation_fragment_component_mix</code>	Category describing what fragments are present in a single experiment. In many cases this will have a 1:1 relationship with a row in the <code>fraglib_component</code> category. An exception is the case of fragment cocktails where one ID corresponds to multiple rows in the <code>fraglib_component</code> category.
<code>_pdbx_fraghub_investigation_fragment_component</code>	Category that lists the fragment components found in each chemical library screened and gives them an ID in-file use. Contains information like names, descriptors (InChIKey), formulae, and molecular weights.

6 Pilot repository for fragment screening

A pilot fragment screening repository

To facilitate the development of the fragment screening data model, we designed, established and validated a pilot repository from fragment screening data that was previously deposited in the PDB: https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/msd/fragment_screening/. In the repository, each file is named after the investigation's accession number, using 'cif' as the extension. The accession number is "Frag_", appended with a unique combination of numbers.

The datasets in the repository were generated by (1) identifying the individual experiments that were part of the same fragment screening campaign, and (2) developing a software application that generates an "investigation" fragment screening PDBx/mmCIF description file from multiple PDB files belonging to individual experiments.

The application has been written in Python and still being developed so alternative files can be used to generate and/or add information to a fragment screening PDBx/mmCIF description file. For example, we have already developed an additional utility component to load information from different data files that contain information about experiments where a

fragment was screened but no structure was deposited to the PDB, and to modify the fragment screening description file with this additional information.

The fragment screening description files were generated from sets of PDB structures that were discovered using two approaches. One approach examines structures deposited to the PDB in 'group deposition' mode. Of 177 of these 'group depositions', 95 were identified as associated with fragment screening experiments, and these were curated based on macromolecule identity, authors, and release date into 71 fragment screening description files. The second approach involved analysis of published data for 'fragment screening' experiments to detect the groups of structures associated with these publications.

Future work

Overall, the created pilot repository will form the basis for refining data models for the fragment screening data capture. The information captured in a fragment screening description file can be utilized in various ways. For example, we can supply precompiled analyses, such as structural superposition of multiple structures from one fragment screening experiment (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Three different fragment screens, which currently have no publication associated with them. Frag_1002047 is a screen against human poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase 14, Frag_1002270 screens against Zika virus serine protease NS3. Frag_1002080 is a screen against human T-box transcription factor T.

Based on this pilot repository, partner EBI will continue to work with iNEXT-Discovery facilities (e.g. FragMAX, EMBL-GR, DIAMOND, etc) to enable their users to easily generate fragment screening PDBx/mmCIF description files as part of their experimental pipelines. We now have an application that generates fragment screening PDBx/mmCIF description files from structures previously deposited to the PDB, that can be modified to capture information from other data structures (e.g. SQL databases, json files, etc). This implies that our application can be modified to handle diverse types of data storage structures being used at facilities that support scientists to perform fragment screening experiments.

The current data structure is flexible and has the capacity to be expanded by exploiting the versatility of the PDBx/mmCIF framework. We are now in discussion with other databases to incorporate fragment-screening non-structure-based experimental results. We will work towards fragment-screening PDBx/mmCIF description files being incorporated into the existing webportal infrastructure used by the wwPDB for the deposition of structures to the PDB. Namely, the fragment screening PDBx/mmCIF description file already contains a specific subset of the information that is needed to deposit a structure on the PDB. This information can be parsed to generate the number of individual deposition sessions (one session per individual structure to be given an individual accession number) that are partially pre-filled with information from the fragment screening PDBx/mmCIF description file. This will greatly aid the deposition of multiple structures to the PDB while capturing the biological context of the multi-structure datasets.

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